

BRAINSTORMING IN TEACHING GRAMMAR (PASSIVE VOICE)

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Abstract. *The article discusses issues related to teaching foreign language grammar, using interactive technologies in this process. The method of brainstorming is considered to be one of the effective interactive approaches in grammar instruction, in particular, passive voice.*

Keywords: *grammar, teaching, passive voice, technology, brainstorming, interactive, approach, foreign language.*

Today, despite the processes of globalization and integration of various methods and innovative technologies in foreign language education, university students experience a certain "linguistic isolation" from native speakers due to limited study time and circumstances that differ from real foreign language interaction, while the interference of the students' native language further aggravates the situation. As a result, students formulate grammatically incorrect sentences and statements, based on the lack of experience and the influence of the native language environment. The solution to this problem requires a comprehensive knowledge of the features, content, means, methods and organizational forms of the process of teaching a foreign language and their application in the practice of higher education.

Grammar as a component of language competence requires students to have a deep understanding of the structure of language. Traditional teaching methods, such as lectures and written assignments, are sometimes insufficient to develop lasting grammar skills. Innovative technologies, including various digital resources, games, collaborative learning platforms, and other active methods, offer new ways to engage students in the process of learning grammar.

In general, pedagogical methods can be classified as follows:

- active - assuming students as "subjects" of learning (independent work);
- passive - not requiring activity from students (lectures);
- interactive - requiring students to interact with each other (projects, problem-based methods).

Interactive learning is a type of learning in which students interact with the learning environment as much as possible, with the teacher acting as a guide for students and assessing their performance. Through this approach, students develop critical thinking and teamwork skills, which contributes to self-realization and the improvement of competencies. Interest in interactive approaches in pedagogy began to manifest itself in the middle of the last century, which was due to the development of technology and a change in views on the content of the learning process, in which the student played the role of a subject rather than an object of education. Traditional methods based on memorization and repetition gave way to more dynamic methods focused on interaction and practical application of knowledge. In the 1960s, under the influence of the communicative approach, more attention began to be paid to teaching language through communication. The theories of the American linguist N. Chomsky on the nature of language and its acquisition stimulated a rethinking of teaching methods. Ideas arose that language should be

studied not as a set of rules, but as a tool of communication. An important step was the introduction of group work and role-playing games, which allowed students to interact, practice speaking skills and solve real problems in the language.

The founder of interactive methods in foreign language education is considered to be the American linguist Charles Curran. He developed an approach called Community Language Learning (CLL) in the 1970s. His methodology was based on interaction and support, where the teacher acted not so much as a teacher, but as a mentor, creating a favorable atmosphere for language learning. Charles Curran drew inspiration from psychology, especially the ideas of Carl Rogers, who emphasized a humanistic approach and the need to take into account the personal needs of the learner.[1] In CLL, students actively communicated with each other and with the teacher, working in groups, discussing real-life topics and helping each other learn the language in a safe environment. Curran's method became one of the foundations for the further development of interactive and communicative approaches that became widespread in the second half of the 20th century and are still used today.

The relevance of interactive teaching methods is explained, first of all, by the fact that the object of education today is the representatives of the "Alpha" generation, surrounded by gadgets from birth. These are children who grew up on digital technologies, whose natural socialization was replaced by a digital environment, which was due to globalization and universal informatization. These and many other factors became the reason for the special educational demand of this generation, which, in turn, explains the emergence of such non-traditional types of education as interactive approaches in the education system in general and higher foreign language education in particular.

There are various interpretations of interactive learning, below we will consider some of them, which, in our opinion, completely coincide with the content of this type of learning. The Pedagogical Encyclopedic Dictionary defines interactive learning as "a type of learning built on the interaction of the student with the learning environment, which serves as an area of the acquired experience." This interpretation, given at the beginning of the century, is supplemented by the definition of researchers Isaev A.A. and Isaeva I.Yu., according to which "interactive learning technologies are such an organization of cognitive activity in which collective interaction of all participants in the educational process occurs, based on problem-based, search and research activities"[2]. Considering interactive learning as an independent approach in educational activities, Korotaeva E.V. and Andryunina A.S. particularly note that interactivity in learning should not be reduced to a method or limited to the use of certain gadgets (such as an interactive whiteboard) and forms (such as webinars, distance learning).[4] Here, we should note the difference between the interactive approach and learning using interactive tools. Classes conducted in the form of business games, trainings, project technologies, problem-based learning are considered interactive activities, however, lessons of a typical traditional format using only gadgets, such as an interactive board, tablet, as well as distance learning are not included in the content of the interactive approach. For, "in such classes, the activity comes from the leader (teacher, lecturer), while the receiving party - in the full sense of the word - has been shifted to those "object" positions"[4]. It should be remembered that the main feature of the interactive approach is that the teacher and the student are considered equal participants in the educational process, that is, learning is of the nature of subject-subject relations between the teacher and the student. As mentioned above, the role of the teacher changes dramatically during interactive

learning compared to traditional methods, since the teacher's functions are limited to organizing the educational process, preparing materials and monitoring the course of events, while students "are enriched with social experience, since they communicate with each other, jointly complete assigned tasks, resolve emerging conflicts, look for common ground and compromise"[3]. Thus, the interactive type of learning provides the opportunity for in-depth acquisition of language units through the active involvement of students in the process.

Interactive technologies, including various digital tools and platforms, open up new opportunities for teaching and learning grammar in English language learning. They provide the means to activate the learning process, address individual characteristics of students and diversify interaction formats. The use of interactive technologies allows to diversify the learning process, making it more dynamic and motivating. This is especially important for future teachers who must master not only the basics of the language, but also the methods of teaching it. Interaction-based approaches allow students to apply theoretical knowledge in practice, which contributes to a deeper assimilation of grammar material. The introduction of interactive methods into the educational process requires future teachers not only to master the technologies themselves, but also to develop adequate pedagogical strategies that will allow them to be effectively integrated into the educational process. Below we will consider several interactive methods and technologies with a detailed description, as well as an outline of the methodological use within the framework of the research topic.

Brainstorming - a method of collectively solving a given problem by generating the maximum number of ideas, while the correctness or incorrectness of the presented idea does not matter much. After the exchange of ideas, the discussion stage begins, then the participants make the best decision. In education, this method is used to develop critical thinking and creative skills. The main principles of the brainstorming method are the absence of criticism at the stage of idea generation, free expression of thoughts, encouragement of the combination and development of the proposed ideas, as well as the maximum involvement of all participants in the educational process. Brainstorming is especially useful because it stimulates creativity, increases interest in the topic, helps to reveal the potential of all participants and improves the quality of teamwork. The effectiveness of this technology also lies in the fact that it does not set any time limits, that is, it can be used both at the beginning of the lesson and in the middle or at the end of the lesson. In foreign language education, in particular, in teaching the grammar of a foreign language, this technique has a number of advantages: students begin to see grammar as a communication tool, and not just a set of rules; the method stimulates active participation and creativity; strengthens the skills of independent use of grammar; allows to jointly search for mistakes and learn from them. The brainstorming method can be effectively adapted for studying the passive voice. The passive voice often causes difficulties for students due to the need to restructure sentences and follow grammar rules, so creative and interactive work with this material makes the process more accessible and interesting. Through interaction and discussion, students develop an understanding of how passive sentences are constructed and how they differ from the active voice, thereby developing a conscious perception of this structure. In addition, in the process of joint work, students repeatedly use the necessary verb forms, which helps them to memorize them. The peculiarities of this technology in studying a foreign language should also be noted in a psychological aspect. The method of brainstorming:

- *removes the barrier*: working together reduces the fear of making mistakes, which is especially important when learning grammar;
- *gives motivation*: students feel involved in the process, which increases their interest in the topic being studied;
- *has a positive emotional impact*: the process of generating ideas evokes positive emotions, which contributes to better assimilation of the material.

When using the Brainstorming method during a lesson, the teacher acts as a leader, which involves creating a favorable atmosphere where students feel free; organizing the work so that each participant has the opportunity to contribute; managing the process of discussing and recording ideas; encouraging students' creativity and activity. The methodological use of this technology takes place in several stages:

1. *Defining the Goal*. Перед началом мозгового штурма формулируется задача, например, генерация предложений, обсуждение применения пассивного залога или выявление типичных ошибок.

2. *Idea generation*. Students offer their own options for using the passive voice within the framework of the assigned task.

3. *Capturing ideas*. All ideas are recorded on a visible surface (board or digital format) for further analysis.

4. *Discussion and analysis*. After completing the idea generation, the group discusses their correctness and selects the most successful options.

5. *Application*. Students apply selected ideas in practice or create new examples, consolidating the material.

There is also the so-called "inverted" brainstorming, in which instead of searching for solutions to a given problem, participants compose questions according to a given grammatical structure, then search for answers to more interesting questions. This type of brainstorming does not limit students to the scope of their own knowledge and, to a certain extent, can reduce the time required for the teacher to prepare for the lesson.[5] Because, in classical brainstorming, the teacher "informs about the essence of the problem being solved 2–3 lessons before the language workshop. ... This is necessary so that students prepare the lexical material and practice scenarios for its application in the communication process"[6]. "Inverted" brainstorming (also called question storming) is relevant today, which is explained by the small number of scientific studies, especially in the field of foreign language education. This technology can be adapted to different levels of foreign language proficiency, and also used in the study of various grammar topics, including the passive voice.

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